

Skills 4 eosc

Milestone: Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues (ELSI) in Open Science: Asynchronous TtT

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Deliverable Abstract

This short report invites comment on the TtT Asynchronous workshops designed by the Skills4EOSC project, WP4, T4.2.

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Milestone: Pilot learning path for Data Stewards

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>

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1 Executive summary

Overview of the TtT asynchronous workshop

On the 3rd of February and the 7th of March 2025, inperson asynchronous workshops were held at Copenhagen University Library (The Royal Library, Denmark) and Copenhagen Business School respectively. The participants were experts in Research Data Management, Law, Data Science, and research support officers specialising in ethical and legal protocols in research projects. All participants were employed at the two aforementioned organisations research support departments.

Participants accessed materials published on the Skills4EOOSC learning platform prior to the workshop. The materials were primarily produced by Sonja Filiposka (UKIM) under the advisement of two legal experts Kasper Drazewski and Marta Musidlowska, both KULEUVEN. The workshop was facilitated on both the 3rd of February and the 7th of March by Mareike Buss (CBS) and observed by Lorna Wildgaard (DKB) and Benjamin Derksen (DKB).

The asynchronous workshop followed the design principle “off the wall”. Off the wall workshops are design and thinking spaces in which participants exchange ideas and solutions, using predesigned materials which follow a sequential structure - no matter if on site or in virtual space. In an “off the wall” workshop, there is no instructor but a host (time keeper) that steers the participants through video lectures and activities plus facilitates methods of gathering up workshop discussions.

The workshops took 3 hours each, including feedback from the participants.

Main areas for Improvement

The workshops at Copenhagen University Library and Copenhagen Business School highlighted several areas for revision. The workshop can be opened up to a broader audience, including PIs, decision-makers, and legal experts, while reducing video time in favor of case-based learning and activities.

The workshop materials in their entirety would take a whole day to complete. Workshop materials. A facilitator is essential to guide the participants through the materials and act as a **content curator** to tailor discussions to fit the backgrounds of the participants. The materials can be used as “a pick-and-mix” to give a more flexible, audience-specific approach to workshop delivery. It could be beneficial to send a preparatory survey to the participants assessing their level of knowledge of OS concepts covered in the workshop materials thus helping the curator prioritise and select content.

The materials require better pacing, improved AI narration, and more inclusive coverage of qualitative research. Specific slides and modules need reordering, simplifying, more animations or graphics and guided questions.

Feedback from the participants

Participants in both workshops underlined the usefulness of potentially sharing a classroom with researchers as well as other stakeholders on the topic.

Participants in the second workshop at Copenhagen Business School had less of an understanding of Open Science concepts, pointing towards the need for a glossary of terms.

Participants from both workshops drew attention to the pacing and articulation of the AI narrator, stating that this mode of delivery made it harder to follow in some areas. They pointed to revisions in the slides as well as the need for extra guidance from the facilitator. They noted as well that it is artificial to draw a clean distinction between ethical aspects and legal aspects.

Comparison to the MVS Legal Expert

The workshop strengthens in particular, the ELSI professionals’ empathy and understanding of the challenges researchers face in working openly. During the workshops at Copenhagen University and at Copenhagen Business School the participants awareness about the different understandings and

application of legal terminology across the organisation, research projects, disciplinary perspectives was improved. The suggested MVS revisions include clarifying the distinction between skills and competences in GDPR and IPR, emphasizing their practical application for PIs. The term “empathy” should be added as a soft skill, as it enhances inclusive policies and researcher support.

The workshop’s relevance extends beyond Legal Experts to MVS RI professionals and Policy Makers, highlighting the extensive legal knowledge required for advising on research regulations.

Sources for asynchronous workshop development

The materials used in the workshop are hosted on the [Skills4EOSC Learning¹ Platform](#) and [openly available in an](#) editable library of training materials in the Skills4EOSC Zenodo. The materials include a Facilitator Guide which includes a list of materials, equipment and content the workshop host is advised to prepare before the workshop. Further, the videos used during the workshop are available on [YouTube²](#) and stored securely in Edumedia, a video library hosted by DKB, and can be embedded using this iframe:

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¹ <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=29>

² <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL2mlGxrtBXixC-Vu96icYtAhlf-2y5xGA>

2 A brief description of the TtT asynchronous workshops and descriptive feedback from the evaluation

2.1 Brief description of TtT workshops

On the 3rd of February and 7th of March, TtT asynchronous workshops “ELSI perspectives in Open Science” were held. The workshops were in person and held at Copenhagen University Library, part of the Royal Library, Denmark and at Copenhagen Business School respectively. Participants were asked to access materials published on the Skills4EOSC learning platform in preparation for the workshops. The workshops followed the design principle “off the wall”. Off the wall workshops are design and thinking spaces in which participants exchange ideas and solutions, using pre-designed materials which follow a sequential structure - no matter if on site or in virtual space. In an “off the wall” workshop, there is no instructor but a host (time keeper) that steers the participants through video lectures and activities plus facilitates methods of gathering up workshop discussions. Mareike Buss was the host for both workshops. As the host is not required to be an expert in the subject matter addressed in the materials, all powerpoint presentations are prerecorded. The content was prepared by experts in the Skills4EOSC project and an AI-generated voice agent presents each slide.

The workshop is defined out of two main parts:

- Self-paced preparatory module (module 00) that contains links to video materials that participants need to review before coming to the asynchronous workshop. These materials provide introduction to the main concepts related to Open Science and ELSI in Open Science. These materials were made available to the participants in digital form at least one week before the workshop.
- The workshop materials include a videos playlist that is used during the workshop together with a supporting learning material in the form of handouts and learning activities. All handouts for the activities in the

various modules were provided physically to the participants during the workshop.

The asynchronous workshop itself consists of 10 modules. The aim of the modules is to provide the information on why ELSI is important in OS and how ELSI professionals can help support OS researchers. The modules are a mix of theoretical information and practical activities focusing on analysis of common ELSI related use cases and scenarios that OS researchers face in their everyday practice. These modules are:

01 – Open Science essentials: the participants are encouraged to join in an activity that acts as an ice-breaker and motivates them to start talking about what they know and have already learned about Open Science and how it is related to ELSI.

02 – The Challenges of Embracing Open Science: ELSI specialists working as research supporters may have a mix of perspectives on Open Science. The purpose of this module is to draw on the challenges they experience or predict in supporting Open Science in research projects and explore them in more depth.

03 – Challenges in applying Legal Frameworks to OS research: Navigating the intersection of legal frameworks and Open Science (OS) can be challenging for ELSI professionals. This module introduces the experiences of OS researchers through role play, helping ELSI professionals understand their motivations and challenges. By seeing OS from the perspective of the researcher, ELSI professionals are better equipped to develop appropriate practical approaches that support OS while upholding legal and ethical standards.

04 – Core values of OS research: The core values of OS are transparency, collaboration, and accessibility to improve the efficiency, reproducibility, and societal impact of research. There are ELSI considerations with each of these core values. In this module the participants discuss privacy, legal frameworks, and equitable access in the context of the OS research core values and how to achieved them while maintaining high ethical and legal standards.

05 – Open Science & ELSI What I need from you: Communication between researchers and ELSI professionals are key for the successful implementation of OS. In this module, the participants role play ELSI professional and researcher. They articulate the challenges they have met in OS research using clear concepts and defining terminology and explain what information they need from each other to solve the identified issues.

06 – Legal Issues related to OS Research: This module addresses legal issues in Open Science which occur when trying to ensure that research practices are ethical, transparent, and compliant with regulatory standards while promoting the responsible sharing and reuse of data. Topics include discussions of safeguarding participants' privacy through adherence to data protection laws, ensuring that intellectual property rights are respected through appropriate licensing and agreement, and how legal frameworks aim to facilitate equitable access to public sector data and support the responsible application of AI technologies.

07 – ELSI in OS: Use-case analysis: This module is designed to explore real-world use cases where topics discussed in module 06 have been successfully addressed, providing participants with practical strategies and tools. By engaging with these case studies and interactive activities, participants will gain a deeper understanding of how to uphold the integrity of research while contributing to the broader goals of open science.

08 – Ethics self-assessments in Open Science: This module focuses on the practical requirements for performing an Ethics self-assessment for EU-funded research projects. The aim is to gain an awareness of possible aspects to evaluate and possible issues in these projects. Participants are asked to evaluate two research scenarios from the perspective of assisting the Principal Investigator (PI) in preparing a self-assessment for a project based on a selection of questions from actual EU self-assessment forms. Engaging with these scenarios will allow participants to test their knowledge in real-world innovative research projects against an ethical background.

09-ELSI Tools and Best practices in Open Science: This training module focuses on implementing the Open Science principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. It covers best practices, such as developing data management plans, using access controls, appropriate licensing. The FAQ activity engages participants in discussions around common dilemmas, such as sharing sensitive data and managing conflicting guidelines. The module aims to equip the participants with practical strategies on how to support researchers in balancing openness with necessary restrictions.

10 – Wrapping up: There is a complex interplay between Open Science principles and the ethical, legal, and societal implications they entail. Open Science practices, such as data sharing and transparency, should be balanced with privacy concerns, intellectual property rights, and regulatory compliance. We sum up this workshop by briefly emphasising the need for practical strategies and infrastructures for navigating these challenges, including developing data sharing agreements, addressing ethical dilemmas in research dissemination, and understanding the broader societal impact of open science initiatives.

The materials used in the workshops can be found on the Skills4EOOSC learning platform and are published in the Skills4EOOSC Zenodo library, please refer to the Executive Summary of this report for more information.

2.2 Workshop at Copenhagen University Library

Four out of nine invited ELSI professionals and Research Support staff took part in the workshop. The profile of the participants were: An ELSI professional from Copenhagen University specialising in support regarding ethical protocols, two data managers from the University Library, a chef research support consultant/engineer from the datalab at the Humanities, one inhouse lawyer specialising in GDPR plus the facilitator, who was a research support officer from Copenhagen Business School.

The workshop took three hours and was held on the 3rd of February, 09:00 am to 12:00 pm, in the teaching room at the University Library, which is a flexible space where the chairs, tables, screens and white boards can easily be moved around. Coffee, tea and snacks were provided.

2.2.1 Observations of the participants' interaction with the workshop materials

01 – Open Science essentials:

The softball, ice-breaker activity was effective despite the participants' diverse backgrounds. While some were legal experts in specific areas, others experts in one discipline while some had interdisciplinary knowledge.

During the ice breaker activity, the topic of FAIR was chosen. The discussion on FAIR principles highlighted varying levels of familiarity among participants. When one participant unfamiliar with FAIR threw the ball, the receiving participant provided a brief introduction and practical examples. This sparked a dialogue on data quality, quality assurance, and local challenges, including available tools.

In the next topic, OS principles, participants explored the inclusion of citizens in research. While acknowledging the value of public participation, they also discussed the potential biases, as only certain segments of the Danish population might be actively involved. The tension between information security and research openness emerged as a key issue, alongside the assumption that data transparency naturally leads to reuse.

Conversations about OS stakeholders questioned the broader purpose of research. Participants reflected on the tendency to focus intensively on their own work without considering its long-term use and impact. Recognizing research as part of a larger system was seen as crucial. Participants noted that research collaborations often introduce unforeseen challenges, making it necessary to continuously update documentation. In clinical research, adherence to good clinical practice is vital, yet researchers often struggle with proper protocol documentation, leading to potential database contamination with poor-quality datasets.

Discussions quickly became political however, touching on institutional guidelines and infrastructure in the light of the current administration reform at the university. The facilitator had to actively keep the discussion on track and encourage the participants to choose new topics. However, it became clear from the very start of the workshop that learning happened during the practical activities and not when watching the videos.

02 – The Challenges of Embracing Open Science:

In the module, the participants noted in a fish-shaped template the concerns they have about ELSI aspects in Open Science. This is called the “Stinky Fish” activity, which we returned to at the end of the workshop to find out if their concerns had become less or increased. During the "Stinky Fish" activity, participants noted topics such as data quality, the risk of scooping, the challenges of anonymizing personal data, and the reuse of datasets across disciplines. Questions were raised about how to share data responsibly, whether Open Science is possible without strict control over personal data,

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and the inherent competitiveness of research. A recurring theme was whether datasets, initially collected for specific purposes, could or should be repurposed, and how to ensure that participants consent to such reuse.

The Stinky Fish

That thing that you carry around but don't like to talk about;

but the longer you hide it, the stinkier it gets.

You should acknowledge and deal with it.

This Photo by Unknown Author is licensed under CC BY-NC-ND

The format of the activity prompted reflection on whether each fish should represent a single concern or if multiple ideas could be assigned per fish. Additionally, the facilitation of the session emerged as a key consideration.

While discussion was lively, a structured approach was needed to ensure all participants had a chance to contribute. Without moderation, conversations risked running over time, potentially leaving quieter participants without an opportunity to share their perspectives. Those who hesitated to speak until the end sometimes found their contributions cut short due to time constraints, emphasizing the importance of structured facilitation and timekeeping.

Despite these challenges, the activity successfully deepened previous discussions from the softball game. The participants eagerly suggested solutions to concerns from their own experiences.

03 – Challenges in applying Legal Frameworks to OS research

This module was a 16 minute long video powerpoint presentation including a 3 minute discussion. The speaker was an AI voice agent.

04-Core values of Open Science Research

This module was a 17 minute long video powerpoint presentation. The speaker was an AI voice agent.

A key takeaway from module 03 and module 04 was the importance of clear communication regarding slide duration – either by the host or in the actual slide presentation. Participants were unsure how long they needed to focus on each slide—whether for five minutes or for fifteen. During the video presentations, the participants looked at their computers, phones, etc.

The effectiveness of the slides themselves is another point of consideration. Across both modules, the speech pattern of the AI-agent detracted from some of the content. It is difficult to listen to the automated voice and digest the information over longer periods of time. Further the amount of information was overwhelming, and was often presented as a list, and sometimes the order of the points discussed on the slide did not always

logical, leading to participant fatigue. Additionally, the use of long, complex sentences—particularly those resembling bureaucratic "EU speak"—risked alienating participants who were already familiar with the subject matter.

On a positive note, the rhetorical style of the text was convincing. However, balancing the length of the video, the scope of the content and the language is essential to keeping engagement of the participants.

05 – ELSI & OS: What I need from you

The use of empathy in this module proved effective, as participants attempted to step into someone else's shoes. However, the exercise was somewhat unbalanced, as one group spoke on behalf of their own experiences while others were asked to adopt the researcher's perspective. Although the group discussions were though very lively, adjustments to the facilitation could help create a more even engagement, ensuring that all perspectives—both from researchers and other stakeholders—are equally explored.

Note – after the completion of the 5th module, there was 30 minutes left of the workshop. Consequently, we chose not to complete modules 06, 07 and 08 and went straight to module 9.

09_Module 9: ELSI tools and best practices in OS

In this module, there is an FAQ activity in which the participants are asked to identify possible ethical and legal dilemmas in a short description of an Open Science research project. However, we did not get as far as doing the activity, as the terminology used on the slides presenting the activity created a somewhat heated, but informative, discussion amongst the participants about the correctness of the information in the activity.

During the FAQ 1 exercise, it became clear that certain terms and concepts needed clarification. The slide conflated GDPR, consent, and anonymisation, which led to misunderstandings. Legally, GDPR governs data usage, not

participation in a project, and mixing these concepts resulted in an inaccurate presentation. To improve clarity, GDPR and anonymisation should be treated separately. Participants also discussed the distinctions between anonymisation, pseudonymisation, and relative anonymisation, as well as how researchers and ELSI (Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications) experts interpret these terms differently. This sparked a discussion, highlighting the need to refine the material for accuracy and clarity.

FAQ 2 addressed the complexities of handling and sharing sensitive data. The session raised questions about defining sensitive data, distinguishing between sharing within a research team versus making data publicly available, and determining whether fully anonymised data can still be safely shared. Participants considered the legal and ethical implications, including the risks of over-anonymisation rendering data unusable. The role of the data processor (datahandler) and responsibilities for secure sharing—such as encryption and controlled access—were discussed in detail. Additionally, the importance of understanding the underlying need for data sharing (e.g., from collaborators or funders) was emphasized.

Module 10: Wrap up

Finally, to close the workshop we revisited the Stinky fish the participants had drawn at the start of the day,

They all concluded that their fishes were still very “stinky” but agreed that they workshop had proven that knowledge of ELSI and support is dispersed across the university and there is a need to improve infrastructures, and decision-makers need to take workshops like this with research support to fully understand the investment needed in such infrastructures, citation:

“We are a lot of people with new knowledge, we need to keep in contact and try to put ELSI issues in OS on the agenda. We cannot lift these activities alone”

2.3 Workshop at Copenhagen Business School

CBS provides business-related education programmes and continuing education for the public and, in particular, the private sector. The five participants in the CBS workshop were from the legal department. One senior, three established and one junior member of the ELSI team took part in the learning path. They advise researchers on ethical and legal requirements in their research projects that can be in collaboration with industry. They work together with a separate research support team who have expertise in how to apply for funding (pre-award team).

Combining our experience and the feedback from the participants from the workshop at Copenhagen University, our approach to the training at Copenhagen Business School (CBS) was different. The Facilitator explored further the role of “Curator”, more details below and in Section 3 of this report. Being the Curator, she selected modules based on her knowledge of the profiles of the participants’, their areas of expertise and how they support researchers at their organisation. Accordingly, fewer modules were used in the training and only certain activities were conducted. As a result, more time was given to discussion which is where deeper learning happens as we observed in the first workshop.

The workshop took 3 hours.

From Facilitator to Curator

A facilitator is essential for the workshop, as participants would otherwise struggle to navigate the materials. However the role of the facilitator goes beyond guiding the participants through the content. The facilitator must understand participant needs and professional backgrounds, ensuring activities, terminology, and learning contexts are relevant, can be clearly explained and presented in the context of the participants. Accordingly, the facilitator takes the role of a “Curator” which demands they have professional knowledge of open science, stakeholder challenges and potentials and skills

as a teacher to be able to explain complex concepts and exemplify these concepts through examples the participants can relate to. Therefore their role is crucial in bridging differences in organisational perspectives, linking prior knowledge to new concepts and practices, fostering meaningful discussions, and adapting the learning experience to the group's specific requirements.

The approach

- The curator motivated the workshop, and advises on how to use the materials on their own after the workshop.
- The curator had an active role during the workshop, both guiding the participants through the activities and videos and also contributing with their professional experiences and cases about ELSI perspectives in Open Science in the context of CBS.
- There were no preparation materials, instead the participants were invited to view the materials on the Learning Platform after the workshop at their own pace
- Only selected content was used, described below. We chose to focus on the activities as these are not self-paced and require a group.

Module 00: Welcome

The Curator kicked off the workshop with short verbal presentation of what Open Science in the context of ELSI. The Skills4EOSC project was presented and the aim of the workshop was motivated. Accordingly, the video Module 00 was not used.

Module 01: Open Science Essentials

The participants enjoyed throwing the ball to each other and choosing themes to talk about from their own experiences. They engaged in constructive discussions. The AI voice/timer occasionally interrupted discussions, suggesting a need for smoother transitions. Despite minimal preparation, participants were familiar with key topics but acknowledged

gaps in their understanding, particularly regarding terminology and legal-ethical distinctions. For example, the FAIR principles needed to be introduced by the senior participant before the other participants could talk about the principles, revealing varying levels of understanding, and the need for further learning.

Discussions on legal issues in open science covered restrictions, licensing, and balancing GDPR compliance with open research, highlighting tensions between legal protection, data security, and privacy. Participants noted that acronyms and categories in the game were unclear and removed from their daily context, making them challenging to interpret. However, they recognized that researchers and legal experts perceive these terms differently.

In conclusion, the game fostered awareness of different stakeholder perspectives, including researchers, administration, society, and policymakers and what these perspectives could mean in the communication of ELSI requirements.

Module 02: Embracing open science

The curator began by showing the video and then conducted the Stinky Fish exercise in which she also created her own Stinky Fish.

The "Stinky Fish" proved abstract for participants without prior preparation or extensive OS knowledge. The participants agreed the ELSI professionals "do not have Stinky Fishes". The observation that "ELSI folks don't have stinky fishes as such" suggests that the exercise may be more effective if researchers are brought into the discussion to provide contrasting perspectives.

As a result the curator and the senior participant engaged in a case-based discussion, that turned into a panel debate where the remaining participants primarily observed. The activity revealed gaps in foundational understanding, such as the distinction between Open Access (OA) and Open Science (OS). The discussions covered research misuse, data security, and

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institutional workflows, with the CBS team noting that OS is not a daily concern for all in their career profile. The discussion further highlighted practical challenges, such as researchers using personal devices for CBS communication despite institutional restrictions.

The participants recognized the need for clearer, more context-driven materials, with stronger involvement from ELSI experts in development. The session ultimately evolved into an active learning experience, emphasizing the importance of establishing a shared foundational understanding before tackling complex OS issues. Moving forward, CBS participants aim to explore OS applications in their specific context and address institutional challenges and opportunities.

After Module 02 the participants needed a 10 minute break

Module 04: Core values in Open Science (shown before Module 03)

The 20-minute video was viewed in full, with discussions centered on the slide “Challenges and Considerations in Implementing Open Science,” which effectively wrapped up key points using pictograms.

The ELSI Considerations slides were particularly well-received for their visual clarity, aiding understanding. However, the AI voice was sometimes too dominant, giving too much information without sufficient alignment with slide content. For example, the graphics in the final 10 minutes effectively illustrated the complexities of Open Science but contained dense information that could be broken down further. Participants suggested splitting the video into two segments: the first 10 minutes before the "Stinky Fish" exercise and the last 10 minutes afterward. Care should also be taken to avoid unnecessary repetition.

Module 3: Challenges in applying legal frameworks to OS research

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The video showcases three researchers' experiences working openly and adhering to legal requirements. These video segments prompted discussions on clarity and relevance.

Segment 1 was well received for its clear explanation of Open Science pillars.

Segment 2 on child psychology was difficult to understand due to poor sound quality.

Segment 3 on FAIR use did not resonate with participants, who were unfamiliar with its requirements despite CBS researchers being mandated to follow FAIR principles. This highlighted a gap in understanding FAIR use and its role in their work.

Participants questioned the overall aim of the video in its entirety and whether they assumed ELSI workers were already engaged with Open Science or acting as advocates. The part about "Challenges in Implementing Open Science" was considered to contain too much verbal information without enough visual support. It was recommended to split this content into three separate slides (Legal Complexities, Ethical Considerations, and Funding Requirements), each with fewer points but stronger visual elements. Additionally, the AI voice was perceived as monotonous, leading to loss of focus. Finally, the distinction between legal, ethical, and funding requirements was seen as artificial, as all points ultimately fall under legal considerations.

To improve engagement, add more animations or graphics to the slides. Provide guided questions to help focus the attention of the participants during viewing and structure discussions afterward.

Lunch break (30 mins)

Module 07: ELSI in OS: Use-case analysis

The Curator introduced the FAQ exercise without a video, and divided the participants in groups of two. The Curator grouped up with the senior ELSI

participant. Each group worked on a specific FAQ, leading to a valuable exchange of knowledge, ideas and experiences between junior and senior participants, with insights contextualized to CBS practices.

- FAQ 1, the group presented their case and solutions, prompting a discussion among the curator and senior participant about stakeholder roles and the balance between archiving and research institutions.
- In FAQ 2, the curator enriched the discussion by drawing on real-life cases, deepening participants' understanding.
- FAQ 3 highlighted gaps in a mock-up form, leading to discussions on the templates CBS researchers use and distinctions between research ethics consent, GDPR consent, and journal code of conduct requirements.

The activity proved highly effective, with discussions planned to extend beyond the workshop, as participants intend to revisit the appropriateness of the templates they use in research support consultations.

Module 10: Wrapping up

The workshop was wrapped up by revisiting the Stinky Fishes produced in Module 02. Notably, not all participants actively contributed, only two added to their fish.

Preferring to discuss the workshop themes as a whole, the participants highlighted a fundamental gap in understanding researchers' everyday realities, emphasizing that professional backgrounds shape perspectives. Participants acknowledged that researchers would likely approach the workshop with different viewpoints and thus require a different selection of modules.

A key takeaway was the tension between Open Science and regulatory compliance, raising the question of whether adhering to OS principles might conflict with established rules and requirements—reinforcing that OS is a consideration rather than a working goal for the ELSI professional profile in Denmark. Additionally, participants reflected on the ELSI role as both necessary and potentially frustrating for researchers, often perceived as the

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raised finger of warning. However, they also recognized that compliance with rules ultimately supports good science.

3 How to improve the workshop materials

In the following section, feedback on the workshops at Copenhagen University Library and Copenhagen Business school are listed.

1. Workshop Design and Target Audience

- The workshop is also suited for PIs, decision-makers at the organisation, as well as Ethical and legal experts.
- The workshop takes longer than two hours.
- Include slides and discussions on how to ensure legal compliance in OS, among other things the necessary infrastructure (human and technological).
- There is potential to develop a version for lawyers unfamiliar with researchers' realities, helping them understand research workflows and priorities.
- Activities worked well, but videos took up too much time—preparatory readings would be more effective.
- Reduce the amount of preparatory materials by recommending selected materials for the participants.
- Add a Glossary of OS terms to the preparatory materials.
- The preparatory materials should cover GDPR, legal challenges in ethics, and consent distinctions (ethical vs. GDPR consent).
- Case-based learning would be beneficial, incorporating EU collaborations, international partnerships, and regulatory challenges.

2. Workshop Facilitation and Content Delivery

- The workshop is not a "plug-and-play" format; it requires preparation and tailoring to the audience by the facilitator.
- The facilitator role is in practice the role of a curator, which entails understanding the profiles of the participants before the workshop. The Curator selects content based on the participants and has enough knowledge of the subject to pose questions, and allow discussions to flow

when valuable. Consequently, know the workshop materials well enough to adjust the workshop agenda “on the fly”.

- If necessary, send a preparatory survey to the participants before the workshop to assess their knowledge and understanding of the concepts covered in the materials. Accordingly, use the responses in the selection of workshop materials and the delivery of these.
- Breaks should be integrated to maintain engagement.

3. Improvements to Workshop Materials

- Ensure the workshop title is consistent across all communication platforms – the Learning Platform, the welcome slides, email communication with participants and GitHub.
- Be more inclusive to the humanities and qualitative research across the slides and in the activities.
- Pre-workshop readings should be clearly structured. In the Learning platform the numbering refers to the origin of the content which comes from multiple sources. Participants found this confusing.
- At the start of the video presentations, inform the listener how long the presentation will take. The facilitator could do this or the information could be added to the first slide in the deck.
- Improve the intonation and pacing of the AI agent voice.
- **About the slides in Module 03:**
 - Shorten the video and reduce the amount of topics covered. Covering so many topics results in listing items to remember. Fewer topics will allow the workshop to delve down into more interesting aspects and improve engagement.
 - Break the content down over more slides with less narration per slide
 - Simplify the language and ensure each slide contributes new information.
 - Correct the order the information is presented on slide 8 “Strategies for Effective ELSI Support”. Either start with the first box on the slide or reorder the boxes in the order in which they are discussed.

- **About the slides in Module 04:**
 - As modul 03. Particularly the subtle changes to the content on the slides “ELSI Considerations” (slides 10 - 12) are not easily identifiable to the learner.
 - Split the video into two segments: the first 10 minutes can be shown before the "Stinky Fish" exercise and the last 10 minutes after the Stinky Fish activity.
 - Split the content “Challenges in Implementing Open Science” into three separate slides (Legal Complexities, Ethical Considerations, and Funding Requirements)
 - add more animations or graphics to the slides.
 - Provide guided questions to help focus the attention of the participants

- **About Module 09:**
 - The FAQs need better clarity, particularly on whether they refer to internal data sharing, external collaborations, or public dissemination.
 - The FAQs are too focused on health research—guidance on adapting cases for other disciplines would help facilitators make the content relevant. Allow the participants to read the handout *before* playing the slides which explain what they have to do. The handouts include clear concept definitions and present the context of the FAQs.

4. Lessons learned from the workshops that may inform the content of future workshops

- Researchers need clearer guidance on what they can and cannot do regarding personal data.
- The assumption that personal data can always be anonymised should be reconsidered, given rapid advances in technology.

Milestone: Pilot learning path for Data Stewards

- Long-term data access and analysis are unpredictable—new strategies are needed to protect individuals while ensuring meaningful research contributions.
- Communication between ELSI experts and researchers is essential to clarify key terms like ethics, anonymisation, and sharing, as well as legal requirements under GDPR.
- The workshop should address regulatory complexities and how Open Science (OS) expectations vary by jurisdiction and discipline.
- Consider a code of conduct module, particularly for administrative staff.
- The workshop should also target research support professionals from different roles, requiring the facilitator is encouraged to tailor the content rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. Tailoring could include, adjusting the the content of the activities such as the subject matter of the cases or simply picking some modules out of the learning materials instead of using them all.

4 Alignment with the MVS Legal Expert

In this section we explore further the alignment between the activities described in the MVS Legal Expert. The term "Legal Expert" encompasses a variety of professionals, including Legal Consultants, Lawyers, Regulatory Affairs Managers, Data Protection Officers (DPOs), and Technology Transfer/IP Lawyers. Each role has varying degrees of legal authority, with some professionals, such as Regulatory Affairs Managers, not always licensed to provide legal advice yet having significant expertise in legal matters. A key aspect of this role is ensuring compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), while also facilitating open access to research materials, data reuse, and collaboration. Legal experts also assist in aligning organizations with legal standards, mitigating risks related to privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations.

In the following comparison, particular attention is paid to which skills and activities are covered in the training and which, if any, are missing in the MVS.

4.1 Comparison of the MVS Legal Expert

Table 2, below, lists how the learning path is supporting elements of the MVS.

Table 2: How the asynchronous workshop supports the MVS Legal Expert

The workshop materials contribute to the following open science outcome for a MVS Legal Expert:

The organization will be equipped with policies, contracts and other instruments necessary to the realization of the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS.

The asynchronous workshop provides material that would help the Legal Expert in the following main activities:

- Promote and support open access and **other OS-related legal and**

<p>ethical principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess and address legal risks concerning Intellectual Property Rights (e.g., Personal and Non-Personal Data Protection and Governance, Licensing and Information Security • Develops policies, contracts and other instruments necessary to the realization of the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS • Advises the organization on the compatibility of local practices with the current legal framework
<p>Essential skills and competencies covered are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good understanding of OS and its practices. • Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (eg the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – ALLEA) • Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data, development and management of policies on privacy and data protection (eg consent forms, data policies, etc) and expert knowledge on the application of regulations on privacy and personal data protection <p>Soft/ transversal skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective communication • Critical and Analytical thinking • Collaboration • Translating needs/bridging function

The workshop addresses the activities and skills above on an individual level, requiring the participant to reflect over their current practices and the regulations and services at their organisation. Below, Table 3, is a list of skills from MVS's Essential skills and competences that are aligned with the skills acquired as a result of the workshop. Primarily, through dialogue and roleplay the workshop, the workshop contributes to the development of the Legal Expert's soft/transversal skills.

Table 3. The alignment between the MVS skills and competencies and the training materials

MVS Legal Expert Essential skills and competences	Covered in training material skills
Good understanding of OS and its practices.	<p>Research Skills: The researchers perspective on working openly but still needing to adhere to the necessary regulations.</p> <p>Fundamental knowledge of Open and FAIR workflows and principles</p>
<p>Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (eg the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity - ALLEA)</p>	<p>Empathy and Understanding: Communication of and reflection over ethical issues in research projects and the complexities of opening research data and documentation in accordance with regulations and ethical principles.</p>
<p>Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data, development and management of policies on privacy and data protection (eg consent forms, data policies, etc) and expert knowledge on the application of</p>	<p>Translating needs and bridging function: Awareness about the different understandings and application of legal terminology across the organisation, research projects, disciplinary perspectives, research groups and individuals.</p>

<p>regulations on privacy and personal data protection</p>	
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4.2 Revision of the MVS Legal Expert

The workshop addressed only a small sub-set of skills described in the MVS Legal Expert, primarily through critical reflection and roleplay the soft skills of the Legal Expert were trained. Training empathy and collaboration in turn should feed into more inclusive policies and improved understanding of the challenges research projects face in application of legal regulations and working open.

We recommend including additional text in the MVS, making a clearer distinction between skills and competences in GDPR and IPR, as during the workshop how GDPR compliance and IPR is applied in practice in research projects is very important and a common issue for PIs, as they have different implications in different stages of the research life cycle.

Further, we recommend adding the term “empathy” as a Soft/transversal skill.

If anything, the training exemplifies how much knowledge is needed to be able to advise on application of legal frameworks and regulations. As such the workshop is also relevant for MVS RI professionals and MVS Policy Maker (in the decision maker and researcher role).

